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Abstract: Alexander Arkadevich is very valuable to us, to the people of Uzbekistan, for his true patriotism of his homeland. The incomparable and unique work of Alexander Feinberg, infused with the best traditions of classical poetry and feelings of love for the land of Uzbekistan, is a special page in the history of our literature.

Key words: poet, feelings, writer, talent, poetry

The famous Uzbek poet Abdulla Oripov said, "As for Alexander Feinberg's work, all the high words do not reflect even a hundredth of the truth, because he was actually a unique poet and translator. A world-class writer, ... none of the Russian-speaking writers can sing a heartfelt song to our sunny land." - described it as.

Collections of his poems are passed from hand to hand, songs based on his texts have been sung, films based on his scripts have been shown, new translations of his works into Uzbek are being made even now. Important dates related to his life and work are celebrated every year, poetry evenings dedicated to the poet's legacy are held.

Why did Alexander Feinberg deserve such popular love and appreciation? First of all, bright, unique poetic talent, high aesthetic level of literary works. The first remained the measure of artistry for Uzbek poets for several decades. It is no exaggeration to say that fourteen sets, numerous performances on stage, radio and television have educated several generations of students.

The poet, whose childhood was spent in the difficult years of the Second World War, was born in Tashkent in 1939. He found an artistic reflection of the kindness and generosity of the Uzbek people in his works. After entering the Tashkent topographical college, Feinberg traveled around the country as a geologist and fell in love with its beautiful nature. It was during this period that his first book "Bike Lane" was published, thanks to which Alexander Feinberg rose to the top ranks of literature in Uzbekistan.

Feinberg graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of the current National University of Uzbekistan and published more than ten poetry books one after the other - "Etude", "Moments", "Press the Sky", "Long Bridges", "Short Wave" and others. Feinberg contributed greatly to the publication of Alisher Navoi's works in Russian in 10 volumes. He also translated the best examples of modern Uzbek poetry into Russian. At the same time, the poet's works were regularly translated into Uzbek, and he became a favorite poet of Uzbek readers. "Chig'ir" (in Uzbek) and other similar collections published in recent years have attracted the attention of poetry lovers as the poet's unique creative writing. Feinberg's contribution to the development of multinational Uzbek literature was duly appreciated by the government. The fact that he was awarded the honorary title of "Honored Cultural Worker of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" is proof of our boundless respect for this great person.

The charm of his poetry has won the hearts of people of very different temperaments, views and ages

I'm swimming, love, far away
Smoke rises from bonfires.
A star can kiss you
I will leave this shore today.
I will throw the anchor on the shore,
Blue water in its wake.
Let's run the waves, ball - ball
The bottom of the river is a literary dream.
Flow along the river,
You look at the sky - birds.
Waves are also a feeling of separation
He grabs one by one as if he sensed it.
Your gray hair is hot,
Smoke from campfire is not visible.
Behind the clouds - the coast:
- Sorry! - it doesn't fit in the blue.

The bright memory of Alexander Arkadevich Feinberg, a wonderful poet, talented translator, caring teacher, will remain in our hearts forever.

LITERATURE:

1. <https://kh-davron.uz/kutubxona/jahon/aleksandr-fajnberg-ya-syn-zemnyx-beregovyx-razvalin.html>
2. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/aleksandr-faynbergning-yorqin-xotirasiga>
3. <https://kitobxon.com/oz/yozuvchi/aleksandr-faynberg>